

Speculation on The Association of a Quantum Oscillator with Phonons

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. April 19, 2025

It is known that classical bound systems have periodicity in time linked with the turning points, because the motion then repeats itself. One may find the period to be $2 \int_{L1, L2} dx / \sqrt{(2m)(E-V(x))}$, where $L1$ and $L2$ are the turning points and a frequency = $1/\text{period}$. For a quantum bound state, one has a discrete energy E_n and a period \hbar/E_n . One may see that in the case of an infinite well potential or quantum oscillator, there is a link between the two frequencies/periods which is not necessarily surprising. Furthermore, a quantum bound state has discrete energy levels and in the case of an electron in an atom, one has photons which lead to excitations between one energy level and another. We thus ask: Why is the quantum oscillator singled out to represent excitations due to phonons simply because $E = \hbar \omega (n + .5)$ with ω representing the classical $2\pi \cdot \text{frequency}$? We note that the quantum bound Schrodinger equation is not the same as $m/2 v(t)v(x) + .5k x(t)x(t) = E$ in the classical case and it is the latter which yields the classical physical angular frequency, ω . Why should the classical ω have anything to do with quantum mechanics other than representing perhaps a mathematical parameter. Certainly the wavefunction $W(x)$ is not sinusoidal like $x = A \cos(\omega t)$, $v = -A \omega \sin(\omega t)$ and so neither is the spatial density $W(x)W(x)$.

We argue that even though $W(x)W(x)$ does not show sinusoidal periodicity, this simply means that one does not have a water-like (or string-like or slinky-like) wave. We argue that $KE(x)_{\text{ave}} + V(x) = E_n$ holds for all quantum energy levels which means that mathematically one has a $v_{\text{rms}}(x)$. We suggest that this statistical quantity has physical meaning in the oscillator case as it shows an intrinsic periodicity which is not due to the classical turning points as in other $V(x)$ classical situations. We suggest that this inherent periodicity suggests in a sense a self-generating wave classically and that if $v_{\text{rms}}(x)$ exists quantum mechanically and can be shown to have this same periodicity $\sin(\omega t)$, then even in the quantum case there are phonons present with the same angular frequency. In the quantum case, the ground state is only half the frequency of the classical ω , but then integer $\hbar \omega$'s are added. They all have the angular frequency ω in keeping with the classical ω . The quantum frequency is $\hbar / (.5\hbar \omega (n + .5))$. If one removes the $.5$ and divides by the classical ω , one obtains $.5\hbar \omega n$, but this is not necessarily revealing because the infinite well potential produces an almost identical result.

Classical Bound State Periodicity

A classical bound state is periodic in time due to the classical turning points. In fact, it is the turning points which create the periodicity in most cases because otherwise one simply has a particle moving with $.5mv(x)v(x) + V(x) = E$ (nonrelativistic case). There is nothing periodic about the motion in a small dx interval even by looking at its math solution, it is only periodic globally because of the turning points with the period being given by:

$$2 \int_{L1, L2} dx / \sqrt{(2m) (E-V(x))} \quad ((1))$$

There is, however, a special classical case, namely the oscillator which has an intrinsic periodicity which has nothing to do with the turning points. For example, for a mass m on a spring with spring constant k , one may give any initial amplitude A (and hence energy $.5kAA$), but the angular frequency is:

$$\omega = 2\pi \sqrt{k/m} \quad ((2))$$

In particular: $x = A \cos(\omega t)$ and $p = mv = -A\omega \sin(\omega t)$ ((3))

This periodicity arises because the conservation of energy equation;

$$.5mv(x)v(x) + .5kx^2 = E \quad ((4))$$

is essentially a modulus squared equation and a modulus is linked with a circle and intrinsic periodic motion. Thus, the oscillator is a special example, even classically, we argue. The oscillator solution seems to be similar to a wave on a string or a slinky. It seems to represent a periodic entity in of itself even though a medium (potential etc) is needed. Unlike the wave on a string or slinky wave, the spatial density is not the signature of the wave, rather it is the sinusoidal $\cos(\omega t)$, $\sin(\omega t)$ which are the signatures.

We suggest that even if one has periodicity in a problem (like all bound state problems classically), that does not mean one has an intrinsic periodic wavelike entity.

Quantum Bound Case

The quantum bound solution follows from the Schrodinger equation:

$$-\frac{1}{2m} \frac{d^2W}{dx^2} + V(x) W = E_n W \quad ((5))$$

Solving for an oscillator $V(x) = .5kx^2$ does not yield a sinusoidal wavefunctions, rather one obtains Hermite polynomials multiplied by $\exp(-.5\sqrt{k/m}x^2)$. Thus, the spatial density $W(x)W(x)$ does not suggest phonons. The quantum energy levels are:

$$E = \hbar \omega (n + .5) \quad ((6))$$

There is an $\hbar \omega$ between each energy level and ω is an angular frequency, but only in the classical solution. It is a math parameter in the quantum case. It is known that all quantum bound states have discrete energy levels and even in the case of an electron in an atom, one states that photons are absorbed or emitted. Thus, the oscillator with constant energy levels does not seem to be anything special. Again, ω is an angular frequency only for the classical solutions $\cos(\omega t)$, $\sin(\omega t)$. The quantum solution does not use these or does it?

We suggest that for all quantum energy levels:

$$KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E_n \quad ((7))$$

Here $KE_{ave}(x) = -1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W$ ((8))

This implies that there exists a mathematical $v_{rms}(x)$ from $KE_{ave}(x) = .5mv(x)v(x)$ ((9))
 We suggest that even though in quantum mechanics one does not follow the particle as $x(t)$, nevertheless $v_{rms}(x)$ should have some statistical significance, just as $W(x)W(x)$ has such significance. If that is the case, then one may show that $v_{rms}(x)$ is the same as the classical:

$$v = -wA \sin(wt) \quad ((9))$$

As a result, in the quantum oscillator there is an intrinsic angular frequency, albeit one associated with v_{rms} . We suggest that this must be of a physical nature and so argue for the presence of phonons with angular w on this basis. These all have the same w and so the energy is built up in that manner. The ground state is the only different case with an energy of $\hbar w/2$.

Quantum Frequency

A quantum bound state has an energy E_n and an angular frequency $E_n = \hbar w$. For the quantum oscillator, one has $w_{quantum} = 2 * 3.14 \sqrt{k/m} (n + .5)$. The classical angular frequency is also $w = 2 * 3.14 \sqrt{k/m}$ which is linked to ((1)). If one drops the ground state .5 piece one obtains;

$$w(\text{quantum without ground state energy}) / w \text{ classical} = n \quad ((10))$$

((10)), however, is not the reason we associate w with phonons, but rather the $v_{rms} = -Aw \sin(wt)$ behaviour. To make this argument, we note that for an infinite square well potential:

$$\text{Frequency classical} = p/(mL) \quad ((11))$$

$$\text{In the quantum case: } p = n * 3.14 \hbar / L \text{ so } ((11)) = (3.14 \hbar n) / (mL) \quad ((12))$$

$$\text{The quantum frequency is; } w(\text{quantum}) = 1/2m (n * 3.14 \hbar) / LL \quad ((13))$$

Thus, the ratio ((10)) is again proportional to n , but this does not prove that phonons are present, as in intrinsic periodic entity in the bound state. The periodicity in the classical infinite well is controlled by the turning points. The quantum solution is oscillatory $W(x) = A \sin(pave x)$, but $KE_{ave} = \text{constant}$ in the well. We suggest that one needs to look at v_{rms} to see if there is a periodic signature.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the harmonic oscillator contains a special periodicity even in the classical case, because it has an intrinsic periodicity in $x = A \cos(wt)$ and $v = -wA \sin(wt)$ which has nothing to do with the amplitude A , i.e. the classical turning points which govern the periodicity

in most bound cases (see ((1))). Thus, periodicity is controlled intrinsically by the angular frequency $\omega = 2 \cdot 3.14 \sqrt{k/m}$ and we suggest that this is like having a periodic entity present, similar to the wave on a string or slinky case, except that spatial density is not the signature here.

In the quantum case, we argue that even though $v = -Aw \sin(\omega t)$ is not used explicitly, it does appear statistically through $v_{rms}(x)$, where $\frac{1}{2}m v_{rms}^2 = -\frac{1}{2}m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} / W$. We suggest then that v_{rms} has physical significance and this significance is an intrinsic periodicity in the system which we assign to a phonon.

We note that $E_n \text{ quantum} = \hbar \omega$ and that one may compare this with classical ω 's, but we suggest that such a comparison does not indicate that one has phonons present.